

Edge AI for Battery Management: Efficient SoC and SoH Prediction for Li-Ion Batteries with Neural Networks*

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Abstract

As battery-driven technologies become more widespread, accurate State of Charge (SoC) and State of Health (SoH) predictions are crucial for effective battery management and predictive maintenance, particularly in resource-constrained edge environments. Traditional methods often rely on computationally expensive processes that are not suitable for deployment on edge devices. This paper presents a novel approach using a single neural network for simultaneous SoC and SoH prediction based on Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurement data and temperature inputs. We conduct a systematic study of neural network architectures, sizes, and quantization techniques to identify the most relevant parameters for efficient operation. The optimized neural network achieves with comparable high accuracy while running on edge devices with a significantly reduced memory footprint and resources, demonstrating the feasibility of advanced battery monitoring in edge AI applications. Our results highlight the potential of deploying sophisticated predictive models on low-resource edge hardware, paving the way for enhanced battery management systems.

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